

Revenue Management Practices in Chain Restaurants

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Abstract

This article examines the definition and fundamental elements of Restaurant Revenue Management (RRM). RRM refers to a set of strategies and practices that restaurants employ to maximize their revenue by optimizing their existing capacities. These strategies include various aspects, such as dynamic pricing, capacity optimization, demand forecasting, strategic menu design, and targeted marketing initiatives. The research was conducted through interviews with eight chain restaurant managers. The findings have been categorized into distinct themes to enhance the structural coherence of the dataset. The results indicate that chain restaurants prioritize effective cost management, menu management, pricing strategies, data management, capacity management, demand management, and tracking performance data within the scope of restaurant revenue management, while never compromising on customer satisfaction.

Key words: Restaurant Revenue Management, Chain Restaurants

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1. Introduction

Revenue management practices have emerged as a crucial tool, particularly in industries with fixed capacity and perishable inventory (Kimes & Wirtz, 2013). (Kimes & Wirtz, 2013). The success of revenue management strategies in the airline and hotel sectors demonstrates their applicability to restaurants as well (Huefner, 2011; Cross, 2016). Since restaurants operate with fixed capacity and perishable inventory (Bolger, 2000), they are ideal candidates for revenue management strategies. As competition intensifies, restaurants must adopt effective revenue management systems to sustain profitability."

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In recent years, numerous studies have explored pricing and capacity management strategies derived from revenue management in food and beverage establishments (Tyagi & Bolia, 2021). These studies emphasize that revenue management applications play a significant role in regulating revenue flows, monitoring business performance, and planning growth strategies in food and beverage enterprises (Kimes et al., 1998; Kimes, 2004; Quain et al., 1999; Heo, 2013; Thompson, 2010). Within this framework, revenue management strategies are generally examined under two main categories: effective capacity management and pricing strategies (Sill & Decker, 1999; Guerriero et al., 2014). Pricing strategies primarily focus on demand-based pricing and price thresholds (Kimes & Wirtz, 2002; Tim & Horky, 2017; Heide et al., 2008; Kimes & Wirtz, 2016). Effective capacity management in restaurants involves optimizing the service process and managing customer demand efficiently; Lasek et al., 2016; Ma et al., 2021; Kim et al., 2020).

Restaurant menus serve as a key tool for increasing business revenue. Revenue management research also investigates how menus should be managed, how prices should be determined, and how menu contents should be selected (Yang et al., 2009; Kwong, 2005; Fang & Hsu, 2014). Revenue management practices are widely recognized as an effective tool for enhancing business profitability (Hanks et al., 1992; Kimes, 2004; Smith et al., 1992). Therefore, it is essential to examine customers' perceptions and attitudes toward these practices in detail for the sustainability of revenue management strategies (Etemad & Durand, 2009; Lee & Choi, 2009; Jiang & Erdem, 2018). If revenue management strategies lead to customer dissatisfaction, they probably result in long-term revenue losses (Kimes, 1989). Finally, information technologies that enhance restaurant operations are expected to support revenue management practices in the restaurant industry (Moreno & Tejada, 2019; Doran, 2010; Kimes, 2008).

The present study aims to address the knowledge gap in this field by examining both the impact of revenue management practices on business performance and their implications for customer satisfaction in chain restaurants. This study seeks to answer the question of why revenue management in the restaurant industry should be examined from both academic and practical perspectives.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Chain Restaurants

Chain businesses are enterprises that operate multiple branches under a unified brand and concept. These establishments deliver standardized services by utilizing identical menus, ingredients, and equipment. The management of chain businesses is typically facilitated through franchise agreements or management contracts (Sökmen, 2005). Chain businesses offer several advantages, including meeting economic requirements, adapting to technological advancements, and integrating specialized expertise into their operations (Koçbek, 2005; Sökmen, 2005).

Similarly, chain restaurants maintain uniformity in brand identity, concept, and service quality, and they are generally overseen by a central management team. To ensure service consistency, central management implements standardized systems, regulations, and controls (Harris et al., 2014; Kurlansky, 2009). Chain restaurants adhere to strict standards in production and operational processes, aiming to foster brand loyalty (Denizer, 2005; Kim & Kim, 2005). Consistent standards increase the likelihood of meeting customer expectations, which, in turn, enhances customer loyalty by ensuring a uniform experience across different locations (Magnini et al., 2010).

Building on this foundation, chain restaurants employ various strategies to enhance brand value. To reinforce customer trust and strengthen their market position, they invest in advertising and marketing campaigns that highlight their brand identity. Additionally, customer service improvements, product diversification, and rigorous quality control measures help maintain consistency while adapting to market demands (Hyun, 2009). These strategic efforts not only sustain long-term customer engagement but also contribute to a competitive advantage by ensuring that the brand remains relevant and appealing across multiple locations.

2.2. Revenue Management in Restaurants

Restaurant revenue management emerges as a crucial strategy aimed at managing customer demand more effectively through capacity management and pricing policies (Kimes, 1989). One of the most important tools for capacity management is reservations. Through reservations, restaurants can manage their capacity efficiently, secure future sales, and implement price differentiation by segmenting customers. Reservations allow restaurants to obtain prior knowledge of customer arrival times and party sizes, enabling more efficient capacity management and minimizing revenue losses caused by empty tables (Quan, 2002). Additionally, the overbooking strategy, also known as "double booking" or "excess reservations," aims to minimize revenue losses caused by no-show customers (Tse & Poon, 2017).

An essential component of capacity management is seating policies. Seating policies are a critical factor that help restaurants fully utilize their capacity and thus increase revenue (McGuire & Kimes, 2005; Thompson, 2015). When the establishment reaches full capacity, waitlist management helps determine seating strategies for customers waiting in line (McGuire & Kimes, 2005; Noone et al., 2009). At the same time, it prevents the loss of customers who do not want to wait or do not have time to wait, thereby increasing customer satisfaction (Iqbal et al., 2012). Waiting time is an important factor for restaurants and plays a critical role for both businesses and customers (Davis, 1991: 421; Tom & Lucey, 1997). Short waiting times enhance customer satisfaction while allowing more customers to be accommodated (Polas, 2018). Waiting time also includes service duration. Controlling service time is a crucial factor in terms of customer satisfaction and

table turnover rate (McDougall & Levesque, 1999). Reducing service time, especially during peak periods, contributes to restaurant profitability by increasing table turnover speed (Noone & Kimes, 2005; Muller, 1999).

Pricing strategies are one of the fundamental elements of revenue management and aim to offer prices to different customer segments based on their perceived value (Kimes, 1999). The dynamic nature of pricing in the restaurant industry arises from the necessity to adapt to fluctuations in customer demand. In this context, variable pricing allows prices to be adjusted according to customer demand in the restaurant industry (Kimes, 2004). For example, the Priority Mixed Bundle (PMB) strategy enables restaurants to increase revenue during high-demand periods. The PMB strategy offers customers with reservations a fixed-price (prix fixe) menu, while non-reservation customers have the option of ordering from the standard à la carte menu. This method allows for the segmentation of customers based on their willingness to pay and enables more effective pricing management (Webb et al., 2023).

Menu management focuses on cost control and increasing sales, while restaurant revenue management optimizes menu demand and pricing (Lai et al., 2020). The costs and preparation times of menu items play a critical role in both variable pricing and operational efficiency (Sill, 1991; Kimes et al., 1998). The activity-based costing (ABC) model proposed by Raab & Mayer (2007) provides product-based cost analysis, supporting restaurant managers in pricing and strategic decision-making processes. Some restaurant chains have used this model to optimize supply chains for best-selling dishes, thereby minimizing product costs while increasing customer satisfaction (Raab et al., 2009).

Additionally, price sensitivity measurement (PSM) techniques enable the development of pricing strategies based on the perceived value of menu items. In a hotel restaurant in Hong Kong, PSM was used to optimize the pricing of a dinner buffet, resulting in a 15% increase in sales (Raab et al., 2009). In another restaurant chain, a value-focused menu pricing model developed based on price sensitivity helped the business reach a broader customer base (Lai et al., 2020). Studies on menu effectiveness indicate that accurate assessments in menu planning, pricing, design, and analysis can enhance profitability (Erdem et al., 2022).

The menu engineering model, as reviewed by Lai et al. (2019) and further explored in Eid (2014), categorizes menu items based on popularity and profitability, providing a structured approach for chefs to decide which items should be promoted or removed from the menu. Eid (2014) highlights how menu engineering integrates with revenue management to dynamically optimize pricing and menu offerings based on consumer demand. Additionally, Raab & Mayer (2007) show that applying activity-based costing (ABC) to menu engineering provides a more accurate assessment of menu profitability by accounting for operational costs beyond food expenses. Restaurant chains strategically implement these principles to optimize their offerings and introduce limited-time products that drive seasonal revenue. For example, Starbucks has successfully applied such strategies to seasonal items like the *Pumpkin Spice Latte*, leveraging consumer

demand to maximize profitability. These insights confirm that integrating menu engineering and revenue management strategies leads to effective decision-making in restaurant operations.

Information technology systems can accelerate restaurant operations and enhance service quality. Particularly, online reservation systems and customer relationship management (CRM) tools contribute to improving customer satisfaction (Altiok et al., 2013). In a study by Queenan et al. (2009), restaurant performance measurement was highlighted as a critical tool for businesses in determining strategies and improving revenue management practices. Metrics such as Revenue Per Available Seat Hour (RevPASH) and revenue per customer help restaurants optimize their revenue management strategies and improve resource utilization (Kimes et al., 1998; Heo, 2016).

The long-term success of revenue management practices depends on businesses continuously monitoring customer perceptions and developing responsive, fair strategies (Noone, 2012). Particularly in pricing, reservation policies, and promotional strategies, adopting fair pricing approaches plays a crucial role in increasing customer satisfaction. Research by Jiang (2014) has shown that customers respond more positively to strategies they perceive as fair, strengthening businesses' reputations. It is essential for businesses to regularly analyze customer feedback and optimize their strategies accordingly to ensure sustainable success.

3. Methodology

This study is based on a qualitative research approach. It aims at understanding the use and operational processes of revenue management practices in chain restaurants. Through interviews conducted with chain restaurant managers, the study seeks to gather detailed insights into revenue management practices and their implementation processes (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2021; Kozak, 2018).

In the study, maximum variation sampling, a type of purposive sampling, was employed. This method aims to select a diverse group of individuals from a small sample size to provide the most comprehensive contributions to the research topic (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2021). Data was collected through semi-structured interviews, which included predetermined questions, and audio recording devices were used for accuracy. The collected data were systematically analyzed and interpreted using content analysis (Bal, 2021).

In this study, semi-structured interviews were conducted with managers from chain restaurants operating across Turkey and, in some cases, internationally. A total of eight interviews were held, seven of which took place in Istanbul and one in Antalya. Istanbul was selected as the primary location for data collection due to the presence of head offices and regional management centers of many chain restaurant brands in the city. This allowed for greater access to senior-level

managers who play a strategic role in revenue management decisions. Despite the interviews being conducted in specific cities, the participating restaurants maintain standardized operations in multiple regions, making the study's findings applicable beyond any single geographic location. Therefore, the research is positioned as a national-level investigation into revenue management practices within the chain restaurant sector.

3.1. Sampling and Data Collection

A comprehensive literature review was conducted to formulate the interview questions, and questions aligned with the research objectives were selected. The selected questions were reviewed by an academic expert and then evaluated by two additional expert academics to ensure validity and reliability. Based on expert feedback, necessary revisions were made, and the final version of the questions was tested through a pilot study conducted with two industry representatives.

Interviews with the selected participants were conducted between September 21, 2022 – October 6, 2022 (seven interviews) and November 24, 2022 (one interview). All participants took part in the interviews voluntarily. Out of the nine participants contacted, eight agreed to participate in the study. The research was conducted with a limited sample of eight participants, primarily due to the small number of full-service chain restaurant managers and the challenges associated with contacting them. However, the diversity of the restaurants managed by the participants increased the representativeness of the data.

The in-depth interview method enabled a detailed analysis of revenue management practices in chain restaurants. All interviews were conducted face-to-face. Audio recordings were taken with prior consent from the participants. During the data analysis process, meaningful statements were carefully selected, their content was thoroughly examined, and key components were identified to reach conclusions. The recorded data were transcribed, and their accuracy was meticulously verified.

Subsequently, content analysis was performed using the NVIVO software, where main and sub-themes were identified. Finally, the findings were revised. This revision was based on the evaluations of two academic experts, ensuring the final version of the analysis.

3.2. Validity and Reliability

To ensure the validity of the study, a semi-structured interview form was developed following an extensive review of the literature on restaurant revenue management practices. The initial version of the interview tool was evaluated by three experts in the fields of gastronomy and restaurant management and revised based on their feedback to enhance content validity. Subsequently, pilot interviews were conducted with two restaurant managers to evaluate the clarity and applicability of the questions. Minor adjustments were made based on their feedback before initiating the full-scale data collection process.

To ensure dependability, all interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent and transcribed verbatim. The data were analyzed through content analysis using NVivo 12 software. Codes were generated both deductively from the literature and inductively from the data through iterative reading and comparison. Themes were identified through categorization and abstraction, and representative quotations from participants were included to ensure the transparency and traceability of the findings.

4. Findings

The managers who participated in this study belong to different age groups and levels of professional experience and hold various positions such as kitchen coordinator, general manager, regional manager, finance coordinator, and accounting coordinator. Their professional experience ranges from 12 to 32 years, while their tenure in their current organizations varies between 6 months and 17 years.

The educational backgrounds of the participants range from high school to university degrees, reflecting a diverse sample. This diversity allows for a broader evaluation of revenue management strategies from different perspectives.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Participants

Participant Code	Age	Education Level	Position	Professional Experience (Current Business)	Total Professional Experience
K-1	51	High School	Kitchen Coordinator	15 years	31 years
K-2	49	High School	General Manager	10 years	32 years
K-3	49	University	General Manager	2 years 11 months	22 years
K-4	43	High School	Kitchen Coordinator	17 years	28 years
K-5	37	University	Regional Manager	6 months	12 years
K-6	37	University	Finance Coordinator	6 years 5 months	13 years
K-7	45	High School	Branch Manager	16 years 8 months	18 years
K-8	50	University	Accounting Coordinator	12 years 5 months	25 years

Source: Created by the authors

The key themes, sub-themes, and related analyses obtained from the interviews are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Qualitative Findings on Revenue Management and Participant Evaluations

<i>Theme</i>	<i>Sub-Theme</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Participant Statements</i>
<i>Functionality</i>	Vitality	Participants emphasized that revenue management is indispensable for ensuring the continuity of business earnings and effectively utilizing capacity.	"Restaurant revenue management is an important issue for the continuity of restaurant earnings." "Revenue management is crucial for the sustainability of restaurant earnings. Revenue must meet the targeted amounts; otherwise, you may have to close the restaurant."
	Revenue Growth	Participants emphasized that revenue management practices, such as pricing, cost management, and monitoring industry trends, play a critical role in business planning processes.	"For an investor to make a profit, they need to proceed with a targeted profit margin. When all costs are accounted for, planning must be done to ensure the desired level of profit." "Revenue management consists of strategies that restaurants implement to achieve their targeted earnings."
	Performance Data	Performance tracking not only evaluates revenue growth but also enables the optimization of factors such as cost control, capacity utilization, and customer satisfaction.	"When implementing revenue management in restaurants, we first evaluate restaurant performance." "Essentially, you receive money in exchange for the products you sell. In a system where cash flow is fast, there must always be management and performance tracking."
	Cost Management	Optimizing purchasing processes, adopting centralized production strategies, and focusing on high-margin products have proven to be effective methods for reducing costs and increasing profitability.	"It is a set of strategies aimed at increasing earnings by effectively managing and controlling costs." "For a restaurant to remain open, pricing must be done correctly, and costs must be well-managed."

Strategies

Procurement	Participants highlighted the contribution of acquiring the right product at the right price to business performance and regarded this approach as a fundamental element of revenue management strategies.	"Revenue management can be defined as purchasing the right raw materials. You must buy products that are both high quality and cost-effective." "My primary revenue management strategy is to increase profitability by purchasing the right product at the right price."
Reservation	Participants emphasized that strategies such as accepting reservations for large groups, directing customers to off-peak hours, and requiring deposits for special occasions are effective in enhancing customer satisfaction and ensuring compliance with reservations. However, it was noted that requiring prepayments for all reservations could lead to customer dissatisfaction.	"We only make reservations when large groups are coming so that we can make the necessary preparations in advance. If a reservation is made during peak hours, we require prepayment."
Capacity Management	The theme of capacity management focuses on strategies aimed at increasing table turnover and optimizing capacity utilization by accelerating service processes. Participants emphasized that efficiently managing all processes from customer entry onward enables us to serve a higher number of customers.	"We do not accept reservations in our restaurants. Instead, we try to assist customers when they arrive, and we communicate this policy to them when they request a reservation."
Demand Management	Participants noted that social media activities, such as sponsored posts and seasonal promotions, are effective in attracting customer interest. In addition to a fixed menu, offering seasonal menus serves as an appealing strategy for customers seeking new dining experiences. However, it was emphasized that discounts and promotions could pose risks to long-term sustainability.	"If there are no available tables when our customers arrive, we try to direct them to the communal table I mentioned earlier." "When all tables are occupied and customers are still waiting at the door, we try to speed up table turnover. To achieve this, all service stages must be executed quickly."
Menu Management	Participants stated that menu design considers customer purchasing power, product costs, popular items, and competitor	"The first factor we consider is whether the prices are suitable for customers' purchasing

		<p>analysis. They emphasized the strategic importance of removing or reevaluating low-performing items and incorporating trending products. The use of seasonal ingredients was highlighted as an effective method for reducing costs while keeping the menu innovative and appealing.</p>	<p>power. Therefore, when determining menu prices, our priority is not product cost but ensuring that items are priced at a level that makes them sellable."</p>
<p>Process</p>	<p>Strategic Management</p>	<p>The theme of strategic management demonstrates that restaurants employ customer-focused approaches and innovative strategies to increase their revenue. Participants stated that they effectively utilize takeaway services, off-site catering, cross-selling training, and social media advertising to enhance customer satisfaction and diversify revenue streams.</p>	<p>"We strive to make our customers comfortable in our restaurants. We renovate restaurant decor and replace worn-out items used by customers." "Our red line in this regard is offering unique products. We aim to attract customers by introducing items they cannot find anywhere else."</p>
	<p>Systems</p>	<p>The software used in restaurants plays a critical role in improving cost management and operational efficiency. Participants stated that these systems enhance efficiency by facilitating sales tracking, calculating product costs, and managing inventory. However, they also noted that the lack of integration between multiple software systems can lead to additional costs and data inconsistencies.</p>	<p>"These programs provide us with all the reports from our restaurants. If a specific report is not available within the system, we request it from the company." "These programs assist us in many ways. When you enter raw materials into the system, it calculates everything from cost to profit margin. The key point here is ensuring that data is entered into the system correctly."</p>
	<p>Database Creation</p>	<p>The process of database creation requires all units within chain restaurants to work in coordination to enhance information flow and operational efficiency. Participants emphasized that regular information sharing between departments such as procurement, R&D, kitchen, finance, human resources, and marketing plays a crucial role in the effective management of restaurants.</p>	<p>"In our restaurants, storage, procurement, R&D, and the kitchen operate simultaneously. We also hold meetings with finance, accounting, food engineers, and field staff during the first week of each month. All operations are managed collectively across all units." "All departments collaborate when necessary. Depending on the area of need,</p>

<i>Performance</i>	Information Management Process	Participants emphasized that information management plays a critical role in increasing restaurant profitability and ensuring operational efficiency. In particular, automation systems enable businesses to quickly detect cost increases, take appropriate actions, and update pricing policies efficiently.	departments can also take individual initiatives." "We have a dedicated team actively conducting market research and income level analyses. At the end of the research, we make collective decisions as a board and then implement them."
	Performance Monitoring	Within the theme of performance monitoring, it was stated that chain restaurants regularly track sales figures and product performance. Managers observe the impact of all changes, evaluate the results, and investigate the reasons behind these changes. Additionally, all operations are monitored consistently, and active communication is maintained with industry peers.	"We regularly track our sales figures. This allows us to actively observe whether the changes we implement have an impact or not."
	Performance Metrics	Performance is evaluated using various criteria, including customer satisfaction, sales volume, profit margins, and the return on costs as profit. These metrics are used to determine the success of restaurants. Restaurant performance is assessed on a daily, monthly, yearly, and seasonal basis. Additionally, revenue per cover, P&L (profit and loss) statements, and sales data are key indicators in evaluating restaurant performance.	"We receive daily restaurant reports. Key criteria we analyze include how many times tables have turned and the average cover charge." "We track how much revenue is generated per cover in our branches and review the P&L (profit and loss) statements of our restaurants."

Source: Created by the authors

The strategies' theme defines which revenue management practices are used in chain restaurants. Research findings indicate that the capacity management theme focuses on strategies aimed at increasing table turnover rate and optimizing capacity utilization by accelerating service processes. In capacity management, restaurants are observed to implement strategies such as social media marketing, promotions, and price discounts to boost customer traffic during low-demand periods.

The demand management sub-theme reveals that flexible and targeted strategies are employed to balance demand fluctuations between peak and low periods. Research findings also highlight that menu management is a critical strategic tool in restaurant revenue management, not only for enhancing profitability but also for ensuring customer satisfaction. The strategic management theme encompasses participants' unique revenue management approaches. The systems theme examines the importance, advantages, and disadvantages of the systems used in restaurant operations.

The process theme covers the flow of information within chain businesses and how this data is processed. Within this framework, the sub-themes of database creation and information management processes emerge. The database creation theme examines the sources of information flow in chain businesses and the collaboration among different departments. The information management process theme includes strategic processes such as cost control, market analysis, profit margin tracking, and information flow within chain restaurants.

The performance theme outlines the performance monitoring processes and criteria used in chain restaurants. Performance evaluations are conducted on a branch basis, considering sales and cost performance. This approach enables comprehensive monitoring of operations and intervention when necessary. The restaurant performance theme is assessed through various metrics, including customer satisfaction, sales volume, profit margins, cost-to-profit conversion rates, and other performance indicators.

5. Conclusions

This study examines the revenue management strategies implemented in full-service chain restaurants operating in Turkey. As part of the research, face-to-face interviews were conducted with eight managers from various management units. The data obtained from these interviews were analyzed using content analysis, categorized into themes and sub-themes. Findings indicate that restaurants employ various revenue management strategies, including reservation practices, table layout and seating arrangements, service processes, customer traffic management, and pricing strategies.

The vitality theme is the first to emerge from the study's findings. One of the primary goals of restaurant revenue management practices is to achieve sustainable profitability. In this context, the findings suggest that effective procurement, cost management, and continuous monitoring of performance data are essential. These findings align with Korucuk and Küçük (2018), who emphasize that process management positively affects restaurant performance. Additionally, they are consistent with Wirtz and Kimes (2007) and Kimes and Thompson (2004), who highlight the necessity of performance tracking in revenue management.

Research findings reveal that revenue management strategies enhance the financial performance of restaurants. In particular, reservation systems, efficient

capacity utilization, and demand management play a crucial role. Effective reservation management provides a significant advantage in cost control and improving customer satisfaction. Participants emphasized that in capacity management, the flexibility and adaptability of table arrangements are key determinants. These findings are consistent with Thompson (2003) and Guerriero et al. (2014). Thompson (2003) highlights that flexible table arrangements enhance revenue and operational efficiency, while Guerriero et al. (2014) argue that dynamic table management is critical for optimizing restaurant revenues. Both studies confirm that flexible seating arrangements help restaurants align with customer demand and optimize capacity utilization.

One of the key strategies implemented in restaurants to increase revenue is demand management. Participants stated that when demand exceeds capacity, they attempt to speed up service to reduce waiting times, which positively affects table turnover rates and customer satisfaction. Previous research by De Vries et al. (2018) and Liang (2017) indicates that long waiting times negatively impact customer behavior and reduce restaurant revenues. The finding that shorter waiting times increase customer satisfaction and encourage repeat visits is supported by Noone et al. (2009), who emphasize the positive impact of increased service speed on customer satisfaction.

Most participants actively use social media during low-traffic periods to increase customer flow. Managers highlighted the role of advertising, promotions, and events in preventing revenue losses. Strategies such as sponsored social media posts, reservation promotions, and menu innovations are used to attract customer interest during off-peak hours. Additionally, concepts such as afternoon tea and happy hour are employed to balance demand, while active upselling by staff contributes to revenue growth. These strategies help reduce imbalances between peak and low-traffic periods in restaurants.

Participants emphasized that in menu management, strategic decisions consider budget, costs, customer expectations, and restaurant location. Pricing is managed using a holistic strategy that incorporates cost-based, market-based, and demand-based pricing approaches. These findings align with Penaflor (2023), who highlights the effectiveness of using multiple pricing strategies simultaneously.

Participants also stressed that interdepartmental collaboration and strong information flow are critical for effective management in chain restaurants. Collaboration ensures efficient process execution while strengthening dependencies between departments. Similarly, Zhao et al. (2001) states that collaboration among supply chain participants improves service performance and reduces costs. The information management process is shaped around market research, cost control, profit margin tracking, automation systems, and rapid response mechanisms, all of which are closely monitored.

Participants evaluate business performance using a multi-dimensional approach, analyzing overall profit at the branch level as well as the sales and profitability of specific products. Customer satisfaction is considered a key performance criterion, supporting the findings of Gupta et al. (2007), who demonstrate that customer satisfaction contributes to revenue growth. In performance evaluations, participants use customer satisfaction surveys, product-based sales and profitability ratios, seasonal revenue data, and per-cover sales metrics. These findings parallel Heo (2016), who proposes performance evaluation methods based on hourly revenue tracking per table, while incorporating a more comprehensive set of analytical metrics.

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the implementation of revenue management strategies in chain restaurants and their impact on business performance and customer satisfaction. By focusing on local industry practices, the study fills a gap in the literature and presents valuable insights for the sector. Future research could further enhance this field by examining the effects of revenue management strategies across different types of restaurants. Additionally, the integration of digitalization and AI-powered management tools into revenue management strategies presents a promising area for innovative research in the restaurant industry.

The functionality theme defines the purposes of revenue management practices. The revenue growth theme reveals that chain restaurant managers view revenue management as a strategic tool for increasing profitability and achieving financial targets. The performance data theme emphasizes the importance of regularly tracking performance metrics to evaluate the effectiveness of revenue management strategies and achieve profitability goals. The cost management theme covers strategies that help restaurants control costs and enhance profitability through revenue management applications. Cost management is a strategic tool that enables financial sustainability and long-term competitive advantage. Lastly, the procurement theme highlights the importance of acquiring high-quality and cost-effective raw materials to reduce product costs and enhance profitability in restaurant revenue management.

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